

Numerical modelling of the viscous fluid-mechanical behaviour of lunar regolith phase change processes, with applications to future Lunar Construction. J. Ting¹, A. Lucca Fabris¹, S. Lim¹

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Introduction: Given the increased interest in Lunar activities through ESA's Lunar Pathfinder [1], China's Chang'e Missions [2], and NASA's Artemis Missions [3], etc., long-term lunar settlement has received recent attention. Thus, promoting a renewed interest in the development of in situ resource utilisation (ISRU) tools.

ISRU defines engineering applications that use local resources, such as basaltic topsoil, referred to as lunar regolith [4]. Such methods are essential for long-term habitation and settlement due to the unsustainability of transporting construction resources to the lunar surface [4].

ISRU has shown promising applications for resource extraction in the production of fuel, water, etc. [5]; as well as for the large-scale construction of lunar settlements [6,7].

Recent research aimed at enabling ISRU-based construction has identified lunar concrete [8], sintered lunar regolith [9], and cast lunar regolith [10] as the most suitable material candidates. Due to the highlighted logistical challenges of transporting resources to the lunar surface and the liquid content commonly found in most concrete-based binders, the following research focuses on non-binder-based manufacturing.

An encouraging approach to enable non-binder lunar construction is the application of digital manufacturing processes, especially additive manufacturing (AM). This is essential due to the hostility and remoteness of the lunar surface [4], which limit most construction and surveying to robotic agents rather than standard construction techniques [11].

Limitations of Current Processes: However, current investigations into construction methods for lunar regolith-based materials (LRBMs) [9,12,13] are still limited. This is due to (i) the absence of standardised metrics for comparing performance across different manufacturing methods; (ii) significant variability in material properties between various processes and multiple investigators using the same process; and (iii) experiments being conducted under laboratory conditions, with limited consideration of future construction applications.

Given these limitations, the following research outlines the development of a simulation tool to model the deposition of molten lunar regolith for potential applications in the additive manufacture of LRBMs.

Viscous Fluid-Mechanical Simulation Tool: The simulation tool has been created using the open-source Firedrake library in Python [14], due to its increased flexibility compared to commercial finite

element tools such as COMSOL Multiphysics [15] and Ansys Polyflow [16].

The simulation has used a pseudo-viscoelastic model to simulate the thermal-fluid-mechanical flow spreading of molten lunar regolith samples. Mechanical properties have been utilised from Schreiner, S. S. et al [17], Bowen, J. et al [18]; as well as results from basaltic lava flows [19].

The simulation tool was then verified against experiments reported in the literature, focusing on the melt-spreading behaviour of sintered lunar regolith simulant cylinders [20]. The simulation tool showed very good alignment with the literature results.

The simulation tool was then utilised to investigate the effects of varying AM processing parameters, such as extrusion temperature and pressure, as well as the external temperature and pressure, with a particular focus on residual stresses, cooling rates, deformation, and post-deposition cracking.

Conclusion: Based on these results, the researcher has drawn three main conclusions. Firstly, careful optimisation of processing parameters will be necessary to enhance both the consistency and quality of the mechanical properties of LRBMs. Secondly, because of the differences between the lunar environment and terrestrial conditions, simulations are essential to understanding the variations in material behaviour. And thirdly, developing a specialised simulation tool for LRBM construction methods will greatly accelerate the development of LRBM processing techniques.

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